

ESSENTIALS OF BIG DATA SECURITY

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Abstract

The rate at which cybercrime is gaining ground globally is very alarming, whilst systems security is paramount in all computing fields irrespective of the technology involved to set up such environments. The importance of computer systems security cannot be over stretched. As a matter of fact, the order of the day and the preaching globally in computing communities is that security must be everybody's concern. The field of computer systems security is growing at a faster rate and a lot more people are moving towards systems security as a profession. Other major factor that makes systems security to be a focal point globally, is the cyberspace that has enveloped computing environments. It requires enormous efforts from all and sundry in the ecosystem of cyberspace to protect all communications elements and resources involved end to end, ranging from source devices, channel or medium of communications and destination devices. Cyber-security is now seen as a compulsory aspect of computer systems to avoid attacks from hackers. This paper will look at the concept of Big Data, Data security and Big Data Security. Also, the tools available to manage big data security, management of Big Data Security, how is Big Data Security implemented and its best practices. Conclusively, the challenges in achieving big data security are highlighted.

Keywords: Big Data, Data Security, Big Data Security, Relational Data, Structured Data etc.

Introduction to Big Data Security

To start with, Big Data can be defined as collection of structured, unstructured, and semi structured data in a centralized or distributed database for information mining and analysis.

The whole point of this is to be able to use data to predict and support machine learning. Big Data is characterized by the large volume of data, wide variety of data and speed at which data is generated, collected, processed and retrieved. With Big Data, operations excellence and better customer experience is guaranteed. As a result, increase in revenue is certain. It is sufficing to say Big Data means large and complex dataset, which can be structured and unstructured that will always require series of analysis to get desired information. Big Data Security refers to the measures and tools needed to safeguard data and analytical methods from malicious attacks, threats, theft, or other harmful activities that could lead to a data breach. In the nutshell it protects the data confidentiality, integrity and accuracy.

According to IBM, about 2.72 million data is envisaged in the near future. This is clearly indicated that data volume will increase astronomically. The security of the anticipated large data volumes will depend on the trustworthiness of the users who will access it.

The paradigm shift has happened and in modern day software development – applications are now data driven. This shift gave rise to the concept of Big Data, thereby making its security extremely important. The increased usage of big data would affect organizations' understanding and application of business intelligence and its security. Security is a major concern nowadays, regardless of the field or technology.

Part of Big data security is the regulatory aspect of data which is either global or local. There is Global Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) which serves as law protecting European data.

Nigeria as a country has Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR). Going against the promulgations by these establishments will result into data breach which may attract penalties of varied degrees. Also,

malicious attacks can affect components, like stored data or the data source. Due to the importance of Big data the adoption rate is on the increase, therefore protection of the big data ecosystem should be considered sacrosanct.

Big Data Security Tools

- **LogRhythm:** It is a big data security analytics platform that combines advanced

analytical methods with cybersecurity expertise to prevent, detect, and respond to potential breaches more effectively than traditional methods. It utilizes machinelearning, AI, and supervised learning methods to identify potential threats and anomalies.

- **BigID:** This is data security platform that provides visibility and control, allowing organizations to reduce risk and remediate data. Data scanning, classification, inventory, privacy automation, and governance capabilities are the features present in

BigID.

- **Varonis:** Varonis offers a data security platform with advanced threat detection, classification, and analytics for big data environments. It helps organizations identify and protect sensitive data, detect and respond to potential threats, and ensure compliance with data privacy regulations.

- **Thales CipherTrust:** This is advanced data security solutions for big data environments, including Hadoop and NoSQL databases. It prevents privileged-user threats and assist to achieve compliance robust security.

- **Protegrity:** Protegrity is a data security platform that offers advanced data protection and encryption for big data environments. It provides data discovery, classification, and tokenization capabilities to help organizations secure their sensitive data and comply with privacy regulations.

Data Security Management

Data security management involves ensuring that business data remains secure and inaccessible to unauthorized individuals. It is a process that guarantee confidentiality, integrity and availability of data. Data security management systems strongly emphasized safeguarding sensitive data, such as private information or

crucial intellectual property for businesses. For instance, developing information security policies, identifying security risks, and spotting and evaluating security threats to IT systems are all examples of data security management tasks.

Sharing information about data security best practices with employees throughout the organization, such as being cautious when opening email attachments, is another crucial Practice.

Big data security implementation

The under-listed below are the basic implementation process to secure any big data platforms:

1. Classification of Data

This is the first stage where a training data set is provided to a classification algorithm to categorize data into two categories, normal and sensitive. This will provide opportunities to identify potential attacks or data breaches. Also data usage history will be leverage upon to determine the category.

2. Encryption of Sensitive Data

In this stage, sensitive data is encrypted with encryption engine so that it is only authorized users will have a decryption engine to translate the data to original form. Cryptography algorithm is used for the exchange of keys between the data source and destination.

3. Data Storage Using ORAM Technology

This stage uses the ORAM technique to store average and encrypted sensitive data on separate system nodes.

4. Path-Hiding Approach on Data Access

During this phase, end-users can use the path-hiding technique to access specific data while maintaining data privacy. The path-hiding technique prevents third parties from guessing data access patterns, securing the overall system.

Security Challenges on Big Data

Security issues can undermine efforts to safeguard and protect Big Data its safety. These issues are not only affecting on premise big data environments, but cloud environments are also not left out on a varied degree of issues plaguing big data ecosystems. It's important to note that these issues aren't limited to on-premises systems.

Typical Challenges to Securing Big Data

1. Human element is one of the major challenges in securing big data. A situation where would be administrator will not for a well-established data governance to extract data.

2. Data theft or breach as a result of not updating the systems security patches regularly.

3. New tools and technologies come with different form of security, which requires new skill set and understanding. To deal with these innovations may require a complicated approach.

4. At times, introducing a security layer brings system slowness in responding to data retrieval, update or delete operations.

5. Also, securing big data attracts additional cost, which may be huge amount of money. In a broader context, comprehensive protection of big data ecosystems will encompass end-to-end security measures. The protection will cut across the data source, medium and destination.

Big Data Security – Best Practices

1. Password Management - Authentication: A well-established password management policy must be followed. This will form a fundamental aspect of big data security governance. It will cover the password length, frequency of the password change and implications of not changing the password at recommended interval, combination of different characters and host of others necessary activities in password management.

2. Access Control Authorization: Access must be well managed. This level of detail is essential because users will consistently authorize necessary access to maintain complete control over the big data ecosystem. Single sign-on is recommended for a big data environment.

3. Segregation of Duties: Users should not hold multiple roles simultaneously to ensure the security of big data. For instance, a system administrator should not possess the capabilities of a database administrator, and vice versa.

4. Data Encryption: Safeguarding data is imperative to prevent theft. Implementing cryptography at various touchpoints is essential to ensure protection across systems.

5. Audit/Logs: The transactional data must be proper logged in audit table objects to clearly store who does what for easy audit. Audit must be performed at regular intervals. Above that a trigger may be implemented to raise an alarm if there is any suspicious act of data violations.

6. Training of Personnel: Training of personnel that will be involved in day to day running of Big data environments are necessary. Additionally, ongoing refresher courses on big data security should be conducted regularly.

7. Threat Detection Systems: Implementing threat detection systems is essential within a big data environment to ensure robust data security. The Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) and Intrusion Protecting systems (IPS) are becoming popular in the era of big data security.

8. Awareness of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR): It is imperative to strictly adhere to the principles and regulations established by data protection authorities, following them precisely. In case of Nigeria, Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR) must be incorporated into GDPR to be able to cater for the international and local regulations.

9. Endpoint Filtering and Validation: Using a mobile device management solution, you can use trusted credentials, perform resource verification, and link only trusted devices to the network. Using statistical similarity detection and outlier detection strategies, you can process malicious inputs while defending against Sybil attacks (one person posing as several identities) and ID-spoofing attacks.

10. Real-Time Compliance and Security Monitoring: By leveraging Big Data analytics, organizations can employ methods such as Kerberos, Safe Shell, and internet protocol protection to actively monitor data in real-time. It's simple to monitor logs, set up front-end

security mechanisms like routers and server-level firewalls and start putting security controls in place at the cloud, network, and application levels.

11. Observation and monitoring play a crucial role in big data security, especially in today's landscape marked by a significant rise in cybercrime. This will serve as additional layers to the afore-mentioned controls.

Identified Security Issues in Big Data

Listed below are the Big Data security issues:

- Data Quality
- Data Storage
- Data Privacy
- Data Theft
- Data Compliance
- Data Audit
- Data Access Control
- Data Integrity
- Data Availability
- Data Management

Conclusion

Data security has become paramount in the digital age when data is increasing rapidly in almost every aspect of human life. The sector is huge and diverse regarding social networking sites, healthcare, retail, and education. Almost everywhere, digitization is taking place, and so are the challenges of security. Security breaches can occur at any stage of data processing, prompting the need for security considerations and potential solutions at each level, spanning from data accu-

mulation to storage, analysis, and processing. Therefore, it is essential to implement best practices and measures to ensure data security. Given the growing frequency of data attacks, organizations must develop a comprehensive Big Data Security strategy. The primary goal of its strategy is to protect enterprise data against internal or external attacks. Enterprises should protect their data from ransomware, DDoS, theft, back door, Man The Middle attack and a host of others.

To effectively secure Big Data ecosystem, controls must be enabled, the software, hardware, network elements and human resources involved must be monitored and observed in agile manners Safeguarding data across all levels is of utmost importance. End to end data encryption and applying cryptography across Big Data environment is essential in order to guarantee Data confidentiality, integrity and availability.

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